

Signals, Action-Reaction and Special Relativity in a Newtonian Framework

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It is possible to obtain special relativistic equations by using the complementarity of frames moving at a constant speed $-v$ relative to each other and thus assuming that there exists an equation linking m_0 in one frame to $E=g(v/c)m_0cc$, $p=g(v/c)vm_0$ in another. In order to have consistent units, one is forced to introduce a constant c with units of speed and this constant should have physical meaning. We have suggested in previous notes that it may be related to a signal which is involved in interactions (such as the well-known signals associated with an accelerating charged particle). We suggest, however, here that one should be able to see these ideas emerge in Newtonian mechanics without the need for the notion of complementarity of frames moving at constant speed with respect to each other.

We first note that in Newtonian mechanics, one has the concept of momentum $p=mv$ which is proportional to the impact made in a collision. We argue that experimentally one can measure mv and as speed becomes large (of the order of c), one would experimentally notice that p is no longer simply mv .

We have argued in previous notes that the Newtonian concept of inertia should be augmented to include rest mass m_0 and kinetic energy in the moving frame. This again requires multiplying m_0 by cc so that it may be added to kinetic energy. Here we consider the simple case of Galilean transformation and argue that even though p is linear in v , kinetic energy is not and that there should be an increase in inertia due to this quadratic nature. This again leads to the question: What is the physical significance of c and how is it linked to an increase in inertia of a moving particle? We argue that the signal c is linked with the Newtonian notion of action-reaction and that for a moving particle, a signal from an applied force moves at $c-v$ (slowing it), while the reaction moves at $c+v$ leading to an imbalance which creates the extra inertia for a moving object with rest mass.

Special Relativity and Complementarity

It is possible to obtain the equations of special relativity by using the notion of complementarity of frames moving at a constant speed of $-v$ relative to each other. In particular, one must equate m_0 in the rest frame with energy E and p (momentum) in the moving frame and this requires introducing a constant speed c so that units are consistent. One then postulates a matrix:

$$\begin{bmatrix} g(v/c) & v/c \\ v/c & g(v/c) \end{bmatrix} \quad ((1))$$

Assuming that a kind of modulus is conserved, one obtains:

$$-m_0m_0cc = -g g m_0m_0 + m_0m_0vcc \quad g g \quad ((2)) \text{ (applying ((1)) to } (0, m_0cc)$$

This result is completely separated from the Newtonian framework, but yields Newtonian physics in the $v \ll c$ limit. The question still remains as to the meaning of c ? Presumably it should represent a physical object which has the same speed in all frames, i.e. does not have rest mass.

We try instead to see special relativity emerge from a Newtonian framework.

Newtonian Mechanics

Newtonian mechanics introduces the notion of inertia, m_0 , (with m_0 being a resistance to force), kinetic energy $\frac{1}{2}mv^2$ and momentum $p=mv$, which is proportional to impact. One may send a moving particle against a target to experimentally determine that $p=mv$ is proportional to impact, but should notice that for very large speed (v of the order of c , the speed of light in a vacuum), that $p=mv$ is not adequate and that it seems that inertia, m_0 , is increasing. We thus ask: Can a Galilean transformation indicate that inertia increases?

A Galilean transformation means that a v (vector) in a rest frame is seen to be:

$V+v_1$ (vector addition) if the rest frame is seen to move at v_1 in another frame.

Here we consider 1-D for simplicity.

In a rest frame, m_0 is inertia, i.e. resistance to force. As seen by a moving frame, m_0 moves and so a force source would also have to move to keep the force physically next to the moving m_0 .

In the rest frame, one considers a $\frac{1}{2}m_0v_0^2$ being imparted to an m_0 at rest (as in a Newton's cradle experiment). The first m_0 ceases moving and the second moves with v_0 .

In the frame which sees the second m_0 as moving with v_1 , the first m_0 moves with v_1+v_0 (Galilean transformation). The momentum imparted is the same.. The idea of kinetic energy being quadratic in v , however, means that kinetic energy under a Galilean transformation does change.

In the frame which sees the second m_0 as moving, a Galilean transformation yields:

$$\frac{1}{2} m_0(v_0+v_1)(v_1+v_0) - \frac{1}{2}m_0 v_1^2 = \frac{1}{2}m_0v_0^2 + m_0 v_1v_0 \quad ((2))$$

Here, $v_0=0$ is the second m_0 speed in the rest frame which becomes v_1 as seen in the moving frame and v_0 is the final speed of the second m_0 in the rest frame which becomes v_1+v_0 due to the Galilean transformation.

Even though $\frac{1}{2}m_0v_0^2$ momentum is imparted in both the rest frame and moving frame under the Galilean transformation, the kinetic energy imparted is different suggesting that more work (see ((2))) is needed in the moving case, suggesting that the inertia has increased, we argue. Thus, it is the quadratic v dependence of KE which leads to an increase in inertia even in a Galilean transformation.

The question then becomes: How does quantify this without using the complementarity of frames?

We have suggested in a previous note that one consider to first order:

$m_{occ} \rightarrow m_{occ} + .5 m_0 v v/c$ as the increase in inertia (multiplied by cc) ((3))

((3)) suggests:

$m(v) cc = m_0 F(vv/cc) cc$ so: $dF/d(vv/cc)$ at $v=0 = 1/2$ and $F(v=0) = 1$ ((4))

To first order: $F(v) = 1 + .5 v v/c + \dots$ ((5))

Furthermore, as argued in a previous note, one wants a pole at $v=c$ so that one cannot exceed a speed of c . This, together with ((5)) leads to a possible solution of:

$F(v) = 1/\sqrt{1-vv/cc}$ ((6)) (as we have already noted in a previous note).

The issue we wish to deal with here is the role of the signal c .

Signal c and Action-Reaction

We have seen that both the complementarity of frames and the increase in inertia due to kinetic energy approaches lead to the presence of a speed c which is the same in all frames and is an upper bound on speed. The question becomes: How does this signal physically account for $m(v) = m_0/\sqrt{1-vv/cc}$? We suggest that it is linked to action-reaction in Newtonian mechanics.

If one has a moving object (rest mass m_0 , speed v) which is being accelerated by a force, one may consider that the force sends out a signal with speed c (speed of light), but due to the movement of the object:

Action moves at $c-v$ ((6a))

The reaction of the particle, however, moves at: $c+v$ ((6b))

Thus, the force gives a slower action and the reaction is faster which seems to imply that one has a greater inertia than if the particle were at rest. Here we make the assumption that the force signal moves at c which is the same in all frames. This is at least consistent with an electromagnetic force. Secondly, $c+v$ means that reaction hits are coming back faster than incoming action suggesting more of a backward push against the applied force.

If the particle is at rest, the action moves at c and the reaction at c . The imbalance now leads to the notion of greater inertia. Quantitatively, however, one needs to use either the arguments of the previous paragraph or complementarity of frames moving at a constant speed relative to each other. Nevertheless, we wish to argue that the presence of c in the theory is consistent with a physical signal which is linked to action-reaction and may qualitatively account for the increase in inertia when an object moves.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that the quadratic nature of kinetic energy $\frac{1}{2}mv^2$, even in a Newtonian context with a Galilean transformation, seems to lead to the idea of a moving object having more inertia. In both the rest and moving frame, the same momentum is imparted, but the kinetic energy change differs, suggesting more work for a moving object, hence more inertia. We note that in a rest frame one has inertia m_0 , but in the moving frame $KE = \frac{1}{2}mv^2$. One should have the same notion in both frames (i.e. that of inertia) suggesting that $m = m_0 \gamma$ be a first order change to inertia. This involves introducing a constant, maximum speed c . (We first show that $1/\sqrt{1-v^2/c^2}$ is a possible solution), but then argue that c is linked with signals from an applied force and reaction from the moving mass which leads to an asymmetry $c-v$ versus $c+v$. This asymmetry gives the sense of an increased inertia for a moving object, we argue.